

ISBE WP10 report

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“Establishment of the curriculum and processes for a
multicentre Systems Biology/Medicine Pilot”

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1. Background

1.1 The role of ISBE in the development of Systems Biology training

The vision of ISBE is to enable Life Scientists from all sectors across Europe to tackle complex biological problems from a systems perspective. Training of scientists, at all levels, in all relevant fields of Systems Biology, is regarded as an essential prerequisite to implement Systems Biology approaches on a broad scale throughout Europe. This will require a major cultural change in training in the Life Sciences in order to develop the integrated approach required to generate the skilled work force necessary to exploit Systems Biology to its full potential. With this in mind, ISBE has hosted two workshops jointly with ERASysAPP to consider these issues in detail and to develop a core curriculum for Systems Biology which is described in WP10 Deliverable 10.2 (An ISBE document which defines a core curriculum for Systems Biology). The aim of this report (Deliverable 10.3) is to describe potential mechanisms for the dissemination and implementation of this core curriculum.

The need for trained staff to manage and operate European research infrastructures has also been identified as a key issue for the effective running and use of these infrastructures. A strategy for training in this area has been developed in discussion with other Research Infrastructures in the Biomedical Sciences and has now been funded by the EC through two H2020 projects; CORBEL and Rltrain.

1.2 Process

As part of Deliverable 10.1 (An ISBE report which reviews the current Systems Biology education), a mapping exercise was carried out to compile a list of training activities in Systems Biology across Europe. It was noted that ISBE had overlapping objectives with ERASysAPP in regard to collecting information about training in Systems Biology and also in regard to the development of a core curriculum for Systems Biology. It was therefore agreed to collaborate with ERASysAPP with respect to these two activities. Deliverable 10.1 was submitted in November 2014 and there are plans to make this information available through the ERASysAPP website and the ISBE community website.

In order to develop a core curriculum for Systems Biology, ISBE and ERASysApp organised two workshops; the first in Heidelberg on 27th and 28th November 2014 and the second in Gothenburg on 23rd and 24th March 2015.

Discussions at these workshops resulted in recommendations for a core curriculum for Systems Biology (Deliverable 10.2). It was noted that interdisciplinary education generally builds on excellence and requires a strong foundation in one of the relevant disciplines thus education in Systems Biology, generally, should start at Master's level. With this in mind, workshop participants developed guidance for (1) the desired entry skills for a Systems Biology Programme (2) the generic skills and competencies that Systems Biology students should have acquired in relevant programmes, (3) educational topics and approaches that would lead to the acquisition of those skills and (4) possible career paths for Systems Biologists.

It was concluded that one of the overriding goals of any Systems Biology education programme should be to develop a student's ability to phrase and communicate research questions in such a manner that they can be solved through the integration of experimental approaches and modelling, and to collaborate productively across different experimental and theoretical disciplines in research and development.

2. Dissemination and implementation

2.1 Mechanisms to address obstacles in Systems Biology education

We have identified several potential mechanisms to facilitate interdisciplinary education in Systems Biology. These include:

- Promoting and fostering interdisciplinary education in high schools and at bachelor level
- Exchange and mobility of teachers nationally and internationally, through multi-centre programmes
- Organisational changes within Universities to allocate teaching resources to specific educational programmes rather than traditional disciplines
- Generating example curricula by international teams of experts and making them openly available
- Generating and exchange of teaching material and resources

2.2 Improving the recruitment of students to multidisciplinary programmes

Considering that the Systems Biology approach to biology and medicine is now widely accepted and has become part of mainstream biology, medicine and bioengineering, it is

imperative to establish active mechanisms for the recruitment of students, the exchange and mobility of teachers, and the generation and exchange of teaching material.

A potential obstacle to recruiting students to interdisciplinary programmes is the lack of exposure to cross-disciplinary approaches in high school and bachelor programmes. Systems approaches, and thinking, needs to be introduced and promoted in high schools and at bachelor level, even if the programmes are mainly oriented towards traditional disciplines. This requires that teachers receive appropriate training in interdisciplinary biology allowing students to improve problem solving skills by synthesizing interdisciplinary tools and evaluating issues from different research disciplines. Teachers should be encouraged to raise awareness of the opportunities and challenges to operate across disciplines in order to solve the biological, medical and bioengineering challenges of the 21st century. Therefore, Systems Biology must urgently reach out, especially in Europe, to education of young people at high schools and at bachelor education. This can be achieved, for instance, by lectures and hands-on training within existing programmes, as teasers, in order to raise interest.

A step forward has been done as the University of Ljubljana (UL), an ISBE partner, organized the event entitled 10th CFGBC Symposium with ISBE and CASyM workshops: “From Functional Genomics to Systems Biology and Systems Medicine” & Hands-on tutorial Systems Biology/Medicine. The tutorial attracted several undergraduate students (14), mostly medical and biochemistry students which will have an impact in the future.

2.3 Mechanisms for collaboration and excellence spreading amongst teachers and trainers in Europe and globally

There is a clear need for closer collaboration and exchange between Systems Biology teachers and trainers. This will be important in order to harmonise and further develop interdisciplinary educational programmes and to make expertise available via exchange of students and teachers.

Training materials and information about courses should also be made available online. ISBE together with ERASysAPP has already made significant effort in this direction. There are plans for the ISBE community portal (<http://community.isbe.eu/>) to disseminate information about training activities in Systems Biology across Europe (D10.1) and ERASysAPP provides a similar platform for exchange of teaching material.

2.4 ERASMUS +

To strengthen collaboration and exchange between the key protagonists in Systems Biology education in Europe, there are plans to develop a proposal for support under the framework of Joint Master Degree action of the new European Educational Project ERASMUS +. This would be a joint Master level study programmes carried out by consortia of European universities.

A survey was conducted in April 2015 resulting in total of 13 Universities expressing interest to take part in a joint Master level study programme in Systems Biology. We have identified the list of available courses, facilities and scientific areas available for the master thesis work and/or internship. It is anticipated that the application will be submitted in March 2016.

2.5 Low-cost networking meetings

ISBE plans to establish mechanisms to promote Systems Biology education at major conferences such as the annual International Conference on Systems Biology. The aim would be to organise a specific forum or workshop in association with major conferences and to develop these in collaboration with other interested parties such as the International Society for Systems Biology and ERASysAPP.

ISBE also proposes to develop a PhD student network in SysBio across Europe with an annual 2-3 days long meeting. The aim would be to establish meetings with a study group format where new developments in Systems Biology research can be discussed between PIs, postdocs and PhD students – along the lines of the young international study group for systems biology: <http://sysbio.brookes.ac.uk/Early%20Career%20ISGSB>.